

Blind Fair Impact Phenomenon (Haonanz Phenomenon)

Probability of Types
Series

Azat Shayak

Independent researcher
B.Eng., The National Research Nuclear University
(former Moscow Engineering Physics Institute MEPHI), USSR
GradDip., The University of Auckland, New Zealand
azatshayaknz@gmail.com, Hamilton, New Zealand

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Before reading the Abstract

This research started with an accidental discovery of a phenomenon. As the investigation was unfolding, more and more findings popped up. The whole research became a continuously unfolding event. For this reason, presenting the exciting findings in the form of an abstract at the beginning of the paper would be the same as showing an audience the final moments of a suspense movie during the first minutes of the film.

For those readers who still want to see the essence of the research before they proceed with reading, going straight to the abstract would be all right. But if you want to experience the same journey into uncertainty, you may choose to read the article first.

Abstract

In a probability system with drawing objects of different types, where all preceding selections of objects are unknown, and an action, applied to the system after a drawing, is fair (same) for any type of objects, the probability of the following outcome can be determined straight away, whether this outcome is a single object or a group of objects in some or without any order. This probability only depends on, and can be found through, the initial proportions of the system.

The phenomenon holds even in the case when the action modifies (but still stays fair) at new instances of drawing.

This phenomenon also works in complex paths with groups of specific outcomes that have unknown selections in between. In this case the blind zones can be ignored and dropped; the groups then require conditional probability as the earlier specific groups affect the probability of the following ones.

Probability trees for solving such problems are in no need anymore due to the straight away answers.

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Introduction. Discovery that triggered this research

In December 2018, a student, whom I was helping with competition problems, stumbled upon a phenomenon in the area of probability while solving a problem. Here is the problem he was dealing with:

“A hat holds 7 blue and 4 yellow marbles. The marbles all have the same size and shape, with the same surface texture, so they are indistinguishable from each other by touch. One marble is removed without looking. Its colour is noted and it is returned into the hat, with two more marbles of its own colour. Then a second marble is removed without looking. Work out the probability that this second marble is blue.” ^[1]

He did not pay much attention to details (he was an ESOL student at the time), and solved the problem as if it were a simple problem of sampling without replacement: no returning a chosen marble into the hat, nor adding or removing extra marbles. Below is a proper solution to this problem:

Figure I-1. Probability tree for solving the initial problem

Here is how Haonan solved it:

Figure I-2. Probability tree for solving the “modified” initial problem

I pointed out to him that although he got the answer right, his solution was wrong. This happens in mathematics. Haonan was not satisfied with my feedback though. He quickly tried different initial numbers, and both approaches (with and without extra action) gave the same answers again! At this point I started realizing that something was happening. I tried a general solution, and there it was: both approaches yielded the same general answer.

The main surprise here, however, was not merely that extra action probability problems are equivalent to the sampling without replacement (when an object is not returned to the system), but that **final** probabilities in all of them (given that the previous results are not known) match the **initial** proportion of that group of objects in the system. This is why probabilities in systems with the same constituents, but different actions, end up being the same. This was an amazing outcome!

The road map of the paper is the following. (For the reason given at the very beginning, the reader may choose to skip the road map as well.) In Chapters 1 and 2, we state and algebraically prove a Lemma that describes this phenomenon. In Chapter 3, we consider the phenomenon from the combinations point of view. Here we obtain a proof

of the phenomenon for the cases of sampling without replacement and reason that proofs, based on this approach, exist for other cases as well. In Chapter 4, we present an interesting model that helps us to see how the phenomenon works; it reveals a certain principle on which the phenomenon rests. A proof based on this principle allows us to include cases of fair environments even with a different action at each instance of drawing an object. Whereas the algebraic proof is purely computational, and the combinatorial proof has both computational and conceptual sides, the proof, based on the principle of similar shapes, is conceptual. In Chapter 5, we see environments in which the phenomenon does not work. These are the environments where the actions are not fair (same) for all the groups of a system, or where some previous blind results become known. In Chapters 6 and 7, we formulate two Blind Fair Impact Theorems that apply the phenomenon to a group of objects to be drawn, whether they are in some order or not, even when they have blind fragments in their midst. In Chapter 8, we formulate the General Blind Fair Impact Theorem that applies the phenomenon to all cases in general. Finally, in Chapter 9, we will see some interesting applications of the phenomenon in probability problems.

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Chapter 1. Definitions. Blind Fair Impact Lemma

1. Let us define **Probability System of Types** (or simply *Probability System* below in the text) as a system with different *types* of objects from which system we randomly draw objects, one at a time, and look for probabilities of selecting certain types of objects.

2. Let us define **Impacts** (or *Impacts of Actions*) as changes that come to bear upon a system after drawing an object from it and applying an **Action** associated with the object drawn.

When a probability system consists, for example, of marbles, after each drawing of a marble, more marbles are added, or some marbles are taken away. Drawing a marble without returning it to the system (sampling without replacement) creates a “take away one marble” impact; there is no follow-up action associated with such drawing. Drawing a marble and putting it back into the system results in a “no impact” to the system because the drawing and returning actions balance each other; the system then remains the same, as nothing happened to it. This is the same with the case of adding one marble of the same feature into the system after a selection.

3. Let us call problems in *probability systems of types* **Blind Fair Impact Problems** (or simply *Blind Fair Problems*) if they meet the following conditions:

- A. We do not know some intermediate results; we are “**blind**” towards them. Our goal is to find the probability of an outcome straight after the blind zone.
- B. Drawing an object sets off an action (including a “no action”) that applies to the group of objects of the same type. This action is the same for any type of object drawn. Therefore, the impact of such action is **fair** towards any type of objects in the system.

It cannot be, for example, adding two blue marbles to the system if the first marble picked is blue, and adding three yellow marbles if the first marble picked is yellow. In this case, the impact to the system will be unfair.

Let us emphasize that “blind” in this paper refers not to the process of picking objects without looking, but to the unknown results of such random selections. The features of drawn objects remain unrecorded; therefore we are “blind” in regards to them.

4. Specific Path Probability Problems are problems where we need to find the probability of an outcome that appears in a certain order (sequence).

For example, a note 50A,50B,50C → BABCAA in this paper indicates that in a system with 50 type A, 50 type B, and 50 type C objects, we are looking for a single outcome that contains 3 A, 2 B, and 1 C objects **in the given order** and the probability of it.

Combo Probability Problems are problems where we need to find the probability of an outcome with a set of objects where the order (sequence) of objects does not matter.

A 50A,50B,50C → 3A,4B,5C (or simply 50,50,50 → 3,4,5) note indicates that in a system with 50 A, 50 B, and 50 C objects, we are looking for an outcome that contains 3 A, 4 B, and 5 C objects **in any order** and the probability of it.

We therefore define **Specific Path** as a specific sequence of objects distinguished by types.

We define **Combo** as a set of objects distinguished by types where an order is not important.

5. “Given that” construction

This section does not give new definitions, but explains the usage of “given that” construction in this paper.

“Given that ...” equals “under a certain condition”, “in a certain environment”. It is the main element of **conditional probability**. Conditional probability in the form of an axiom states that $P(A \cap B) = P(A | B) \times P(B)$, where $A \cap B$ is the joint intersection of events A and B, and $A | B$ is event A given event B ^{[2],[4]}. In Kolmogorov’s definition of the conditional probability of A given B, $P(A | B) = P(A \cap B) / P(B)$, “the logic behind this equation is that if the possible outcomes for A and B are restricted to those in which B occurs, this set serves as the new sample space” ^[3]. In other words, “this equation is understood as the fraction of the set $A \cap B$ to the set B” ^[4].

Now, by using Bayes’ theorem ^[5] $P(A | B) = \frac{P(A)P(B|A)}{P(B)}$ as a tool, let us swap A and B in the axiom above, so that we can apply the axiom to the sequential systems covered in this paper, where event A occurs first, then event B. (The axiom works in sequential systems as well: “A and B occur together, although not necessarily at the same time” ^[2].) Let us also swap two probabilities after the equation symbol in the axiom above for the same reason: an independent event in sequential systems precedes the following conditional event. Now the axiom looks a bit different: $P(A \cap B) = P(A) \times P(B | A)$. With the added wording, and after being applied to our sequential systems, $P(\text{both independent event A and dependent B occur}) = P(A) \times P(B, \text{ given that A has taken place})$. Finally, since in our probability systems letters A and B are also used for labelling different types of objects, let us replace A and B in the axiom with event 1 and event 2.

In summary, in this paper we will use the following: $P(\text{both independent event 1 and dependent event 2 occur}) = P(\text{event 1 and then event 2 occurs}) = P(\text{event 1}) \times P$

(event 2, given that event 1 has taken place) = $P(\text{event 1}) \times P(\text{event 2 in a new environment after changes wrought by event 1 modified the original environment})$.

In the Theory of Probability nowadays the term *event* is used to denote “a collection of possible results” ^[6], “a subset of the sample space” ^[7]. In this paper we will use the ordinary, free of probabilistic terminology, definition of this word. We can name it *single event* in order to distinguish it from the above term. Therefore, we will avoid, when possible, the word *event* and use the phrase *single event* instead.

As we have mentioned above, A and B in this paper indicate two groups (types) of objects, representatives of which groups make a sequence or a combo of objects. If A, for example, represents a group of marbles of aquamarine colour, and B represents marbles of blue colour, then a record AB**B indicates that in an experiment of pulling marbles from a container, the 1st marble is aquamarine, the 2nd one blue, the colours of the 3rd and the 4th ones are unknown, and the 5th marble is blue. Altogether, there are five single events in this experiment.

Overall, representatives of group A and group B in a sequence of objects drawn represent different single events, but additionally, an outcome A and another outcome A also represent two different single events (as well as B and B in the example above). This does not violate the principles of conditional probability.

It needs to be noted that the | symbol is used in this paper both in $P(B | A)$ notations and for introducing comments. This should not cause confusion because both usages are easily distinguishable.

Let us now set forth a lemma that describes the phenomenon, with which our story and investigation have begun.

Blind Fair Impact Lemma. *In probability systems with objects drawn, where impacts are fair (same for any type of objects), the probability of a single outcome, such that all outcomes prior to it are unknown, is not affected by these blind results, but depends directly on the initial characteristics of the system, namely, proportions of the system that are given by the size of the groups (types of objects). This probability is denoted by the size-based proportion of the group, to which the outcome belongs to, in the initial system.*

The lemma holds even in a case when a fair impact modifies at new instances of drawing an object.

In other words, such probability can be calculated in spite of the fact that an observer is blind towards the results of selections that have taken place before the final outcome.

Later on we will formulate Blind Fair Impact Theorems that apply to a group of objects to be drawn, whether they are in some order or not, even when they have blind fragments in their midst.

In the following chapter we give the first proof of the Lemma.

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Chapter 2. Algebraic proof

Let us revisit this problem using the simplest action, sampling without replacement, where a marble drawn is not returned, no additional marbles are added or taken away, and let us get the general solution for the probability that the second marble drawn is blue. (In this research we use only the simplest case of sampling without replacement: drawing one object from a system without replacing it. Drawing two or more objects simultaneously without a return is out of the boundaries of this paper.)

So, a hat holds b blue and y yellow marbles. One marble is picked without looking and then removed from the system. Its colour goes unnoticed. Then a second marble is picked without looking. Work out the probability that this second marble is blue.

Let *total* stand for the total number of marbles in the system initially. $Total = b + y$. In the diagram B and Y stand for blue and yellow types of marbles.

Figure 2-1. Probability tree for two groups with the case of sampling without replacement

$$P(2^{\text{nd}} \text{ marble is blue}) = P(BB) + P(YB) = \frac{b}{total} \times \frac{b-1}{total-1} + \frac{y}{total} \times \frac{b}{total-1} = \frac{b}{total} \times \left(\frac{b-1}{total-1} + \frac{y}{total-1} \right) = \frac{b}{total} \times \frac{b-1+y}{total-1} = \frac{b}{total} \times \frac{total-1}{total-1} = \frac{b}{total} = \text{initial proportion of blue marbles in the system} = P(1^{\text{st}} \text{ marble is blue}).$$

$P(2^{\text{nd}} \text{ marble is blue}) = P(1^{\text{st}} \text{ marble is blue})$ is quite a remarkable statement! We are heading to the even more exciting $P(\text{last marble is blue}) = P(1^{\text{st}} \text{ marble is blue})$.

Pay attention to how $\frac{b}{total}$ factorizes, and the other factor at the top of fractions, the created one, cancels out with the second denominator. This shows a mechanism of returning to the initial proportions.

Now we extend the problem and try it with three groups of initial objects. This time we have a system with r red, b blue, and g green marbles. Let $total$ stand for the total number of marbles initially in the system. $Total = r + b + g$. In the diagram R, B, and G stand for red, blue, and green types of marbles.

Figure 2-2. Probability tree for three groups with the case of sampling without replacement

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(2^{\text{nd}} \text{ marble is blue}) &= P(RB) + P(BB) + P(GB) = \frac{r}{total} \times \frac{b}{total-1} + \frac{b}{total} \times \frac{b-1}{total-1} + \\
 &\frac{g}{total} \times \frac{b}{total-1} = \frac{b}{total} \times \left(\frac{r}{total-1} + \frac{b-1}{total-1} + \frac{g}{total-1} \right) = \frac{b}{total} \times \frac{r + (b-1) + g}{total-1} = \frac{b}{total} \\
 &\times \frac{total-1}{total-1} = \frac{b}{total} = \text{initial proportion of B in the system} = P(1^{\text{st}} \text{ marble is blue}).
 \end{aligned}$$

It becomes apparent that for any number of groups the mechanism of simplification remains the same. The initial B branch (that relates to the group of interest) in the tree diagram always produces the $\frac{b}{total} \times \frac{b-1}{total-1}$ term of the probability sum. All other initial branches (that relate to other groups in the system) produce

$\frac{[\# \text{ of objects in that group}]}{total} \times \frac{b}{total-1}$ terms. After adding all the terms and factorizing the

numerators, we get the familiar $\frac{b}{total} \times$

$$\frac{[\# \text{ of objects in the first group}] + \dots + [\# \text{ of objects in the last group}] - 1}{total-1} = \frac{b}{total} \times \frac{total-1}{total-1} = \frac{b}{total} .$$

Here is a solution when an action is different from sampling without replacement (extra marbles are added or taken away):

Figure 2-3. Probability tree for a system with any fair action

The general $+k$ covers all actions. For example, a marble is not returned ($k = -1$), or when the marble is returned and some more marbles of the same colour are added ($k = 2$, in the initial problem). Obviously, when $k=0$ (a marble is returned after being picked) the system stays unchanged and the results hold.

$$P(2^{\text{nd}} \text{ marble is blue}) = P(BB) + P(YB) = \frac{b}{\text{total}} \times \frac{b+k}{\text{total}+k} + \frac{y}{\text{total}} \times \frac{b}{\text{total}+k} = \frac{b}{\text{total}} \times \left(\frac{b+k}{\text{total}+k} + \frac{y}{\text{total}+k} \right) = \frac{b}{\text{total}} \times \frac{b+k+y}{\text{total}+k} = \frac{b}{\text{total}} \times \frac{\text{total}+k}{\text{total}+k} = \frac{b}{\text{total}} = \text{initial proportion of blue marbles in the system} = P(1^{\text{st}} \text{ marble is blue}).$$

Here, the same mechanism that returns the probability we are looking for to the initial proportions is at work: $\frac{b}{\text{total}}$ factorizes, and the other factor at the top of fractions, the created one, cancels out with the second denominator. Whatever is added to group B, is also added to the whole system, *total*. This is why the changes to group B, shown at the top of fractions in $b+k$, and the changes to the system, shown at the bottom part of fractions in $\text{total}+k$, match each other. At the same time, all the initial branches of the probability tree that are different from group B jointly contribute (together with $b+k$) to making $\text{total}+k$, which becomes a factor at the top part of fractions. These two factors, at the top and at the bottom, cancel each other out.

Let us go further and get the general proof for any number of groups. We are still covering the case where the first object has been picked, and an action has been applied to the system.

The mechanism of simplification remains the same. The initial B branch (that relates to the group of interest) in the tree diagram always produces the $\frac{b}{\text{total}} \times \frac{b+k}{\text{total}+k}$ term of the probability sum. All other initial branches (that relate to other groups in the system) produce $\frac{[\# \text{ of objects in that group}]}{\text{total}} \times \frac{b}{\text{total}+k}$ terms. After adding all terms and factorizing the numerators by taking b outside the brackets we get

$$\frac{b}{total} \times \frac{[\# \text{ of objects in the first group}] + \dots + [\# \text{ of objects in the last group}] + k}{total + k} = \frac{b}{total} \times \frac{total + k}{total + k} = \frac{b}{total}.$$

This is an amazing outcome. Regardless, whether a chosen marble is returned or removed, and whether on top of it more marbles are added or taken away, the result is not dependent on these actions. It always adheres to the initial characteristics of the system: the proportion of marbles of a desired colour in the system initially.

Now we can generalize this to any number of sequential actions. On one hand, we can do it by using the same approach of drawing a probability tree for two rounds of selections, and then showing that the mechanism of simplification and returning to the original $\frac{b}{total}$ is exactly the same. It would not be difficult to show that for any number of sequential selections the mechanism of returning to the original $\frac{b}{total}$ stays the same.

Yet here is a shorter approach. We have already seen that after the impact of the first action, the probability of picking up an object from a group of interest is the same as the proportion of this group in the system initially. In our example, group B was an arbitrary choice, thus any group in a system possesses this feature.

Therefore, after the impact of the first action we obtain a new system in which the proportions of groups behave and act in the same way as the initial ones. In reality, the proportions of groups in the system change after the first round because one object has been selected, and an assigned action has impacted the group to which the object belongs to. Yet, because this selection and, therefore, the impacted group are unknown, the system becomes theoretical, where the initial proportions of groups theoretically remain the same. (We will see this theoretical model in details in Chapter 4.)

If a ratio of groups produces the same theoretical ratio after an action, then after the following action, given that this new action is also fair (it may differ from the previous action), the theoretical ratio will again stay the same. This same ratio will keep appearing after each new action, even if there are an infinite number of such actions.

Thus, the probability of picking an object of an arbitrary type after a series of blind selections is equal to the probability of picking this object at the first attempt.

The findings may feel very counterintuitive because a system keeps changing after every random selection, but the final probability stays the same. Yet, because these selections are unknown, the theoretical proportions of the system hold.

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Chapter 3. Combinatorial approach

Let us consider a couple of interesting proofs that involve combinations and permutations. Although these proofs work only for systems with sampling without replacement, they still well illustrate the above phenomenon. By the way, if an impact were different but still fair, for example, adding two extra marbles of the same colour after each pick, or the changing impacts were of some pattern and still fair, then it would

be, very likely, still possible to generate the new *combinations and permutations formulae* for such a system, and the proof would still stand.

Before we start with a combinatorial approach, let us see an example of using it in a text book [8] first.

Four chocolates are chosen at random from a box containing six with hard centres, and eight with soft centres. Calculate the probability that three of the chocolates have soft centres, and one is hard-centred.

Solution: The number of ways of choosing three chocolates with soft centres and one hard-centred one is $C_3^8 \times C_1^6 = 56 \times 6 = 336$. The total number of ways of choosing *any* four chocolates from 14 altogether is: $C_4^{14} = 1001$. Probability (three chocolates have soft centres, and one is hard-centred) = $\frac{336}{1001} = \frac{48}{143}$.

Now we apply this approach to a Blind Fair system. In an example, there are 10 blue and 7 yellow marbles in a hat. Marbles are taken out without looking, one at a time; they are not returned to the hat. The first three selections go unknown. What is the probability that the fourth marble taken in this way is blue?

In order to find the answer, let us first answer a different question: What is the probability that among the first four marbles picked, one is of blue colour, and the other three are of any colour?

$$P(1B \text{ and } 3*) = \frac{\text{the number of selections of } 1B \text{ and } 3* \text{ from } 10B \text{ and } 7Y}{\text{the total number of selections of any } 4 \text{ marbles from } 17 \text{ altogether}} =$$

$$\frac{\text{the \# of selections of } 1B \text{ from } 10B \times \text{the \# of selections of any } 3 \text{ marbles from } 16 \text{ remaining ones}}{C_4^{17}} = \frac{C_1^{10} \times C_3^{16}}{C_4^{17}}$$

$$= \frac{40}{17}.$$

The probability exceeds 1, and yet this makes sense. The reason it exceeds 1 is the overlap of combinations. Four possible arrangements (B***, *B**, **B*, and ***B) produce duplicates. For example, b_1^{***} that is a part of B*** also appears in b_1B^{**} , $b_1^*B^*$, and $b_1^{**}B$. This “unacceptable” result is addressed below, whereupon it still serves as part of the solution.

Only one of these arrangements (B***, *B**, **B*, and ***B) is of interest to us, ***B. Also, remember that because we are dealing with combinations, the number of arrangements within each group of B***, *B**, **B*, and ***B is exactly the same. All the possible arrangements in three gaps of B*** will be exactly the same as in three gaps of *B**, or **B*, or ***B. In order to see it more clearly let us specify B from marble to marble. The above is true for b_1^{***} , $*b_1^{**}$, $**b_1^*$, $***b_1$. It holds for b_2^{***} , $*b_2^{**}$, $**b_2^*$, $***b_2$ and works all the way to b_{10}^{***} , $*b_{10}^{**}$, $**b_{10}^*$, $***b_{10}$. If each specific case adheres to the rule, then the whole as an aggregate is subject to this rule as well.

$$\text{Therefore, } P(***B) = \frac{40}{17} \div 4 = \frac{10}{17} = \frac{\text{the original number of blue marbles}}{\text{the total number of all marbles}} = P(B \text{ at the } 1^{\text{st}} \text{ pick}) = P(B).$$

When we take the probability of only one of these four cases (B***, *B**, **B*, and ***B) all the duplicates are cut off, and we get the pure probability of P(***B).

The generalized proof for this approach is in [Appendix 1](#).

And right away, as a branch of the proof above, we get another elegant proof: Since the number of combinations of $***B$ is the same with $B***$, then $P (**B) =$

$$\frac{\text{the number of combinations of } ***B}{\text{the number of combinations of } ****} = \frac{\text{the number of combinations of } B***}{\text{the number of combinations of } ****} = P (B***) =$$

$=$ |the probability of $B*** =$ the probability of B at the 1st go and any other three afterwards from the remaining marbles $=$ the probability of B at the 1st go| $= P (B) \times P (**, \text{ given that } B \text{ has been selected at the } 1^{\text{st}} \text{ go}) = P (B) \times P (\text{any three marbles from the remaining ones}) = P (B) \times 1 = P (B).$

To make it shorter, $P (**B) = P (B***) = P (B).$

It is natural to try to link $P (**B)$ with $P (B)$, yet it is not obvious to compare $P (**B)$ and $P (B***)$ instead. From the point of view of combinations, $P (**B)$ and $P (B***)$ are the same.

When we substitute $***B$ with $*..*B$ (where $*..*$ stands for any number of blind gaps), and $B***$ with $B*..*$ in the proof above, and set that B represents any group of interest, we get the generalized proof for this combinatorial approach.

It has been mentioned earlier that if an action that is different from sampling without replacement or a sequence of actions of some pattern were still fair, then it would very likely be possible to generate the new *combinations and permutations formulae* for such a system, and the proof would still stand. Although generating such formulae for each different pattern of actions is not practical, we can illustrate, through an example here, that the combination or permutation approach in such cases would still work.

Consider a simple probability system: one object in a group with feature A and two objects in a group with feature B. An object is picked from the system without looking, and then it is returned to the system with one more object of the same feature. Using the permutation approach, find the probability that the second object picked has feature B.

Figure 3-1. Probability tree for illustrating the permutation approach

Our first task is to list all possible permutations of B^* . (We need to clarify here that a specific path of types consists of all possible permutations of specific objects that fit the specific path.) These come from the lower branch of the probability tree: $b_1a_1, b_1b_1, b_1b_2,$

b_1b_3 (generated by b_1), and $b_2a_1, b_2b_1, b_2b_2, b_2b_3$ (generated by b_2). The b_1b_1 case means that b_1 came up at the first pick, and then at the second round it was picked again. There are 8 cases in total.

This time we list permutations of $*B$. They come from both branches of the tree. From the upper branch we get a_1b_1 and a_1b_2 . At the lower branch are b_1b_1, b_2b_1 (ending with b_1), b_1b_2, b_2b_2 (ending with b_2), and b_1b_3 and b_2b_3 (ending with b_3). There are altogether 8 cases for $*B$ as well.

Groups B^* and $*B$ share 6 cases; they also have 2 unique cases each.

The next step will be listing all possible permutations of any two specific objects: $a_1a_1, a_1a_2, a_1b_1, a_1b_2, b_1a_1, b_1b_1, b_1b_2, b_1b_3, b_2a_1, b_2b_1, b_2b_2, b_2b_3$. They make 12 cases in total.

We can now see that since both B^* and $*B$ have the same number of permutations, $P(B^*) = P(*B)$, the same as in the case of sampling without replacement.

Moreover, $P(B^*) = P(*B) = \frac{8}{12} = \frac{2}{3} = \frac{\text{the \# of objects in B group}}{\text{total \# of objects in the system}} = \text{Probability of choosing a B object at the 1st pick} = P(B)$.

Also, similar to the earlier “elegant” proof, $P(*B) = P(B^*) = P(B)$.

One counterintuitive feeling that arises when we apply a combinatorial approach to probability systems is this: combinations and permutations are something stationary and void of changes, whereas probability systems keep changing. To address this feeling, let us again use the example above. The fact that there are more objects in the B group compared to A (two versus one) determines that among all possible permutations of B^* and $*B$, more permutations will be coming through the lower B branch:

Figure 3-2. Interrelation between a changing probability system and stationary permutations of objects

Therefore, the “stronger flow” at the lower branch of the tree is reflected in a larger number of permutations produced by the larger group B.

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Chapter 4. The principle of similar shapes

4.1 An interesting model that helps to see how the phenomenon works: fractions of objects

Let us consider an unusual model that will help us to see a principle on which the phenomenon rests.

We begin with a simple case for an easy introduction. Consider 10 red, 10 blue and 10

green cards constituting a deck of cards. One card is picked without looking. The card does not go back into the deck. Afterwards, a second card is picked. What is the probability that its colour is red?

Figure 4-1. Probability tree for the introduction problem

The action of drawing the first card equally applies to all colours. The probability of being picked equally spreads among three groups of cards. We can represent the system after the first action as the one, where one card in each group loses its one-third (one-third is torn off). So, theoretically (which is also blindly: we do not know what the first selection was), after the impact of the action at the first picking we now have $9\frac{2}{3}$ cards of each colour in the deck. What is the chance of getting a red card at the next attempt (second pick)? $\frac{1}{3}$!

Let us now consider a probability system, where numbers differ from group to group. A hat holds 4 red, 3 blue and 2 green cards. One card is removed without looking, it is not returned to the hat. Then a second card is removed without looking. Work out the probability that the second card is blue.

Figure 4-2. Probability tree for the model with fractions of objects

After the first pick each colour loses a fraction of it proportionally to its weight in the system. After picking a card and removing it we theoretically get $4 - \frac{4}{9} \times 1 = 3 \frac{5}{9}$ cards of red colour, $3 - \frac{3}{9} \times 1 = 2 \frac{6}{9}$ blue cards, and $2 - \frac{2}{9} \times 1 = 1 \frac{7}{9}$ cards of green. Then, what is the probability of getting a red card on the next attempt? $3 \frac{5}{9} / (3 \frac{5}{9} + 2 \frac{6}{9} + 1 \frac{7}{9}) = \frac{4}{9}$. This is the proportion of red cards in the initial system.

It is not difficult to see that 4, 3, and 2 factorize in their expressions above. The other factor is exactly the same for all groups, and cancels out in the final fraction that gives the probability.

$$(4 - \frac{4}{9} \times 1) / (4 - \frac{4}{9} \times 1 + 3 - \frac{3}{9} \times 1 + 2 - \frac{2}{9} \times 1) = [4 \times (1 - \frac{1}{9} \times 1)] / ([4 \times (1 - \frac{1}{9} \times 1)] + [3 \times (1 - \frac{1}{9} \times 1)] + [2 \times (1 - \frac{1}{9} \times 1)]) = 4 / (4 + 3 + 2) = \frac{4}{9}$$

When we replace 4, 3, and 2 with general a, b, and c (we can use any number of different groups), they undergo the same process of simplification, and return to the original ratio. Thus, such systems retain their initial ratio of groups.

After the first step, each colour group loses a fraction of cards proportionally to the initial ratio of cards, or in other words, proportionally to its “weight” in the system. The initial numbers **decrease proportionally** according to their initial ratio so that the new ratio stays the same. This occurs after each step. After any number of steps, the initial ratio holds.

This can be likened to a shrinking of a triangle. All sides are reduced according to their lengths so that the initial ratio holds. What we get after such shrinking is a new, smaller triangle that is *similar* to the original one; it possesses the same ratio among the sides.

We can generally say that added to the system objects (or oppositely, objects to be removed) are proportionally split according to the ratio of the initial groups and distributed among these groups. This keeps the ratio of the groups and the ratio of the changes to them uniform. As a result, the system keeps its proportions.

4.2 Features that ensure proportional equivalency in the model

These are the key features of the model that provide equivalent transitions from one state in a blind fair system to another in terms of proportions of groups.

1. The groups of objects have their proportional weight in the system (expressed through numbers).

2. Impacts, related to the groups of objects, have probabilities of happening that reflect the proportions of groups in the system.

The initial ratio, in our case 4 red, 3 blue and 2 green cards, applies not only to the initial cards, but also determines the probability that a certain colour will be impacted. In 4 out of 9 cases, the impact applies to red cards, in 3 out of 9 to the blues, in 2 cases it applies to the greens.

3. When proportions are applied to the action in the system, which is the same for any group (for example, taking away one object from the system), they produce proportional gains/losses to the groups in the system.

In other words, the fair impact that comes upon an unknown group gets shared among all groups of the system according to their proportions in the system. Thus, the shared impact produces proportional changes to the groups.

4. The initial proportional groups experience the correspondingly proportional increase/decrease of objects. We get a new system (with hypothetical numbers) that is proportionally equivalent to the previous system.

5. After the new ratio of groups is simplified, it is the same as the ratio at the beginning. This keeps the same initial ratio in the system, no matter how many steps of action we take.

The most important key in this model is this: proportional sharing of the added to (or removed from) the system objects among the groups provide proportional changes to the proportional sizes of groups. This keeps the proportions of the changing system unaltered.

We can name this model “a model with hypothetical numbers” for future references.

4.3 Inclusion of fair environments with a different action at each step

So far, we have considered fair environments with the same action at each step. The phenomenon can also be used when the fair action changes (but still stays fair to all groups) at new instances of random selection. We will call impacts of such actions *variable fair impacts*.

Consider this example:

A hat holds 7 blue and 4 yellow marbles. One marble is picked without looking, and returned into the hat with five more marbles of its colour. Then a second marble is picked without looking. This time the selected marble and one more marble of the same colour are removed from the hat. Then a third marble is picked without looking. Work out the probability that this third marble is blue.

The conventional solution with a probability tree gives the probability $\frac{7}{11}$.

Let us apply the reasoning from above to this problem. After the first action, the parameters of the system in terms of proportions stay the same, 7 to 4 (ratio of blues to yellows). Although five marbles have been added, the system keeps its proportions. Now we change the action, and fairly apply it to the new system where 7 to 4 holds. Whatever the new action is, the parameters of the system will stay the same: 7 to 4. The actions that follow may change again, but the proportions of the system will hold.

Here is how it is seen through the use of hypothetical numbers. When the chances are applied to the 1st action we get: $7 + \frac{7}{11} \times 5$ blue and $4 + \frac{4}{11} \times 5$ yellow hypothetical marbles. After the 2nd action we get: $7 + \frac{7}{11} \times 5 - [(7 + \frac{7}{11} \times 5) / 16] \times 2$ blue and $4 + \frac{4}{11} \times 5 - [(4 + \frac{4}{11} \times 5) / 16] \times 2$ yellow hypothetical marbles. The first denominator, 11, is the initial total objects of the system; the second denominator, 16, is the new total after adding five extra marbles to the system as the first action. As for the numerators, 7 and 4 factorize in them; the “leftovers” are exactly the same, they cancel out. The new ratio simplifies to the initial 7 to 4. When we replace specific numbers with general a, b, c, ... for any number of groups, the exact same factorization and simplification apply, and a system returns to its original ratio of a : b : c : ...

4.4 The principle of similar shapes and a proof based on this principle

The reasoning presented above introduces the principle of similar shapes. Let us briefly recapitulate the main points from the previous sections.

Each group in Blind Fair systems retains its proportional size (weight) while impacts (probabilities of which are proportional to the weight of groups) take place. (This is somewhat similar to Physics, where heavier objects produce heavier impacts. The strength of an impact produced by an object is directly proportional to the object's weight.) Proportionate impacts produce proportional changes brought upon the groups. Thus, groups and changes to them are aligned in this regard: they are linked to the same proportions. As a result, the ratio of groups in the changing system remains constant. We see in such systems the principle of similar shapes (by analogy with similar triangles). In systems, where an action does not change, "similar shapes" keep getting smaller and smaller (or larger and larger) with the same coefficient. In systems where actions change, "shapes" get larger, smaller, larger, etc., but the proportions stay the same.

The principle of similar shapes (keeping the proportion of the interest group in the whole system the same at each new step of the system) allows us to generate another proof for our phenomenon, that $P(*[n \text{ gaps before } B]*B) = P(B)$, where B represents an arbitrary interest group.

Indeed, $P(*[n \text{ gaps before } B]*B) = P(*[n \text{ unrecorded selections}]*) \times P(B, \text{ given that } n \text{ drawn objects have gone unrecorded prior to it}) = |\text{moving blindly from a pick to another pick keeps the initial ratio of groups in the system, therefore } P(B, \text{ given that } n \text{ drawn objects have gone unrecorded earlier}) = P(B \text{ at the } 1^{\text{st}} \text{ pick})| = P(\text{any } n \text{ objects have gone unrecorded in } n \text{ drawings}) \times P(B \text{ at the } 1^{\text{st}} \text{ pick}) = 1 \times P(B \text{ at the } 1^{\text{st}} \text{ pick}) = \frac{\text{the number of objects in } B \text{ at the beginning}}{\text{total number of objects at the beginning}} = \frac{b}{\text{Total}} = P(B)$.

Since B represents an arbitrary group (type of objects), the proof generalizes. The proof is now complete.

As we have seen in this chapter, the proof applies to any fair action system, including those where the action varies from one instance of drawing an object to another.

The algebraic approach in Chapter 2 can prove the inclusion of variable fair impacts as well, but the principle of similar shapes here allows us to visualize this inclusion.

Is it not interesting that among different proofs, although generally they prove the same thing, some of them prove or highlight additional features? Besides, this feature of *variable impacts* is very useful.

In terms of the nature of our proofs, the algebraic proof is computational, the combinatorial one has both computational and conceptual sides, and the proof, based on the principle of similar shapes, is conceptual.

4.5 Overcoming counter-intuitive feelings

Let us also consider a couple of examples that may give unsettling feelings about our counter-intuitive findings.

An extreme example

The action now is adding 100 marbles of the same colour after a marble is drawn. If a blue marble is drawn at the first random selection, then most certainly after any number of selections, the outcome will be a blue marble because at the second step we already have 107 blue and only 4 yellow marbles in the hat. But, with the probability of $\frac{4}{11}$, the first marble drawn may be yellow! Then it is almost certain that after a number of steps the final marble will be of the yellow colour. So, 7 to 4 still holds.

An example with taking away

Imagine now an action of taking away 10 marbles of the same colour after selecting a random marble. For example, there are 70 blue and 40 yellow marbles in the hat at the beginning. Choosing one colour breaks the balance towards the other colour; at the second drawing the chance of picking the other colour becomes higher. It looks like there is a shift towards an inverted ratio, and proportions of groups become somewhat opposite to what they were at the beginning. But when the other colour is picked sooner or later, the proportions return towards the initial ratio. Overall, the initial proportions stay the same.

4.6 Two distinct models of fair invariable impact systems in action

Let us call probability systems *Fair Invariable Impact Systems* (or simply *Fair Invariable Systems*) if they meet the following conditions: the impact is fair, and stays the same after each instance of drawing.

There are two distinct models of fair invariable systems in action: one with minimal increment (or decrement), another one with extreme ones. Here are some considerations on how they work.

We can view the first type of system in action as a balanced flow. Consider an example: there are 90 red and 10 green solid balls in a bag. One ball is taken at a time without looking, it is not returned to the bag. What do we expect to see among the 10 first balls picked? The expected numbers (in terms of probability) are 9 reds and 1 green. After getting 90 balls, we expect to see 81 red and 9 green balls. In the remaining 10 there are expected to be 9 red and 1 green balls. According to our hypothetical numbers model, at the time of the last ball selection, it is expected to see there the $\frac{9}{10}$ th fraction of a red ball, and the $\frac{1}{10}$ th fraction of a green ball. When we join these fractions together, we can say that in this ball we expect to see $\frac{9}{10}$ th of it having red colour, and $\frac{1}{10}$ th having green. Hence, what is the probability that the very last ball picked is red? It is 9 out of 10. $P(\text{***[99 gaps]***R}) = \frac{9}{10}$. This is the same as the initial proportion of the red balls in the system. All of the above can also be extrapolated to a system with the minimal increment where one more ball of the same colour is added to the bag after each selection. In both cases there is **a small and gradual proportional decrease or increase of the size of groups** in the system. Theoretical proportions after each action hold.

This time we have an extreme case. There are 7 blue and 3 yellow small balls in a bag. One ball is picked without looking, and then returned to the bag with additional 100 balls of the same colour. It is easy to foresee that the second ball chosen will most likely be of the same colour as the first ball since the number of such balls has increased by a hundred. The superiority of the group of the first drawn ball will steadily grow at every

new selection. What is the colour then of the last ball drawn in an arbitrarily chosen number of random selections? Almost certainly the colour of the first ball. What then are the probabilities for the colours of the first ball? The probabilities are that 7 out of 10 it will be blue, and 3 out of 10 yellow. Therefore the chances for the last drawn ball (when we do not know the colours of the preceding ones) are still 7 out of 10 for blue, and 3 out of 10 for yellow. These (7 and 3) are the initial characteristics of the system. In such models the first selection determines the final outcome. The first one itself depends on the initial proportions. We can label such systems as “the-first-pick-determines-the-last-outcome”. **In spite of a huge increment, the hypothetical sizes of the groups still grow proportionally.**

All other models place themselves in between these two edges. Both groups, the edge models and the ones in between, bear the same feature: the last outcome with unknown preceding selections entirely depends on the initial proportions of the system because of its proportional enlargement or shrinking.

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Chapter 5. When the phenomenon does not work

5.1 When not fair: breaking the principle of similar shapes

The action at each step should be the same for each group of objects. It cannot be, for example, adding 5 red marbles after a red marble is picked, 3 blue marbles after a blue marble is picked, and 2 yellow marbles when a yellow colour is picked. In this case, the proportions of changes to the groups (see the mechanism of it in work in the following example), which proportions determine the ratio of new hypothetical numbers, differ from the proportions of initial groups, and therefore the transformed theoretical system (with hypothetical numbers) acquires new, different from original, proportions.

Let us look at the example that we used at the very beginning, and introduce unfair actions to it.

There are 7 blue and 4 yellow marbles in a hat. A blue selection causes the addition of one more blue marble, a yellow selection four more yellows. When we apply the chances to the first action, we get $7 + \frac{7}{11} \times 1$ blue and $4 + \frac{4}{11} \times 4$ yellow hypothetical marbles.

The new ratio of marbles now is $7 \frac{7}{11}$ blues to $5 \frac{5}{11}$ yellows. When simplified, it is 7 to 5, and this is different from the initial ratio 7 to 4. The proportions break, “shapes” are not similar anymore, and the Blind Fair approach cannot be used. If we want a ratio of objects that follows an impact staying the same, then the action of adding or removing should be exactly the same with each group. In unfair systems the proportions keep changing.

Here is one more reason why a new proportionally equivalent system cannot be created in unfair environments. Proportionally shared (split) new added objects are applicable to fair systems because no matter what type is selected, we know that the whole system gains (or loses) a certain number of objects. We apply proportions to that number (and by doing this get hypothetical new numbers). In unfair systems, the newly

added (or removed) objects cannot be shared at all because there is no exact number of such new objects. We get one number if the selected object is red, another number if the object is blue, and so on. In unfair systems, one cannot get the number of added to (or removed from) the system objects at the next step. Therefore, splitting the indefinite number of objects is impossible.

5.2 When not blind: specific path cases

The phenomenon is not applicable in systems where we know results of some preceding selections. In that case, we are not blind anymore. (Yet, the phenomenon still works in fragments of partially blind, partially specific paths.)

For example, two marbles are drawn in succession from a bag that contains 3 red and 4 blue marbles. We need to calculate the probability that the first marble drawn is red and the second one is blue.

The common approach provides this solution:

Figure 5-1. A common solution for a non-blind probability problem

An attempt to apply the Blind Fair approach fails here:

Figure 5-2. An attempt to use the Blind Fair approach in a non-blind environment

The Blind Fair approach for P (2nd B) covers both B outcomes, RB and BB, not RB only.

The revealed outcome (“the first marble drawn is red”) does not allow spreading its impact proportionately among all the groups (as it affects only one specific group) and thus breaks the initial proportions of the system.

The problem above can be solved though by applying the Blind Fair approach two times in succession. After the first drawing P (Red) = $\frac{3}{7}$. The system has changed now, becoming 2 red and 4 blue. Now we can apply the Blind Fair approach to the new system: P (Blue) = $\frac{4}{6}$. The total probability P = P (R) x P (B in the new environment) = $\frac{3}{7} \times \frac{4}{6}$. Although blind zones here become of length zero, they are still counted. The solution path becomes exactly the same as the conventional one.

This approach also reminds us that specific path probabilities have their own easy formula.

To find the probability of BBRRBRB path in the probability system above, we use the following formula:

$$P(\text{BBRRBRB}) = \frac{b \text{ [the initial amount of B]}}{\text{Total marbles}} \times \frac{b-1 \text{ [for the 2nd element in the path]}}{\text{Total}-1} \times$$

$$\frac{r \text{ [the initial amount of R]}}{\text{Total}-2} \times \frac{r-1}{\text{Total}-3} \times \frac{b-2}{\text{Total}-4} \times \frac{r-2}{\text{Total}-5} \times \frac{b-3}{\text{Total}-6} = \frac{4}{7} \times \frac{3}{6} \times \frac{3}{5} \times \frac{2}{4} \times \frac{2}{3} \times$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{1}.$$

Each island in the formula represents the probability formula for the new updated system at each new step.

Let us label *easy formula* here with quotation marks, “easy formula”, as we will refer to it a few more times in this paper.

When an action after a selection, for example, is returning a marble into the system with two extra marbles of its colour, then probability of specific path NNMNNMNM in the environment with n navy blue and m maroon marbles is

$$P(\text{NNMNNMNM}) = \frac{n}{n+m} \times \frac{n+2}{n+m+2} \times \frac{m}{n+m+4} \times \frac{n+4}{n+m+6} \times \frac{n+6}{n+m+8} \times \frac{m+2}{n+m+10} \times \frac{n+8}{n+m+12} \times$$

$$\frac{m+4}{n+m+14}.$$

The point here is that we do not need to draw a probability tree in order to find the probability of a specific path, because it is represented by only one single route along the tree. Its probability can be written down step by step directly. In this regard, the “easy formula” is simply a step by step description of this single route (a specific path) in the probability tree.

So far we have used the Blind Fair approach for problems with a simple outcome: finding the probability of an object with a certain characteristic appearing at the end. Yet, there is more to this phenomenon.

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Chapter 6. Partially blind, partially specific paths - Blind Fair Impact Theorem for Specific Paths

Highly interesting, the Blind Fair Impact approach is still part of the solution for partially blind, partially specific path problems.

6.1 A specific path after a series of blind outcomes

A hat holds 7 red and 5 blue marbles. Five marbles are removed one by one without looking; their colours are unknown. What is the probability that the fourth marble removed is red, and the fifth one is blue?

$P(\text{the 4}^{\text{th}} \text{ marble is red, the 5}^{\text{th}} \text{ is blue}) = P(\text{***RB}) = P(\text{***R}) \times P(\text{B, given that ***R has taken place}) = P(\text{R}) \times P(\text{B, given that ***R has taken place})$.

Is given that ***R has taken place the same as given that R has taken place? How does ***R affect the following B?

We have two parts here, *** and R. The blind zone ***, according to the similar shapes principle, fairly affects all groups and does not change the initial ratio of groups in the system. Therefore, it does not affect the probability of to-be-drawn objects afterwards, particularly the probability of picking B at the fifth step. Selection R means that one R has been removed from the system. All of this allows us to say that given that ***R has taken place is equivalent to given that R has taken place.

Given that one R has been removed from the hat, the system changes. Then $P(\text{B, given that one R has been removed})$ is the probability of B in the changed original system, which has been modified by removing one red ball.

Thus, $P(\text{***RB}) = P(\text{***R}) \times P(\text{B, given that ***R has taken place}) = P(\text{R}) \times P(\text{B, given that R has taken place}) = P(\text{R in the old system with 7 red and 5 blue marbles}) \times P(\text{B in the new system with 6 red and 5 blue marbles}) = \frac{7}{12} \times \frac{5}{11} = \frac{35}{132}$.

Since $P(\text{***RB}) = P(\text{R}) \times P(\text{B, given that R has taken place})$ then $P(\text{***RB}) = P(\text{RB})$.

We can continue with a case where the specific path gets longer. We can use the same example as above, and this time find the probability of getting the fourth marble red, the fifth one blue, and the sixth marble red again.

As in the previous case, the *** zone does not affect the probabilities of the upcoming objects to-be-drawn.

$P(\text{***RBR}) = P(\text{***R}) \times P(\text{BR, given that ***R has taken place}) = P(\text{R}) \times P(\text{BR, given that R has taken place}) = P(\text{R in the old system with 7 red and 5 blue marbles}) \times P(\text{BR in the new system with 6 red and 5 blue marbles}) = P(\text{R in the old system with 7 red and 5 blue marbles}) \times P(\text{B in the newer system with 6 red and 5 blue marbles}) \times P(\text{R in the newest system with 6 red and 4 blue marbles}) = P(\text{RBR}) = \frac{7}{12} \times \frac{5}{11} \times \frac{6}{10} = \frac{7}{44}$.

We can see that for any length of a specific path, the procedure remains the same: as soon as we reach the specific path the system updates at each step, and we get the probability we look for by using an “easy formula” for specific paths.

“One outcome” approach proof.

Another good approach here is to consider RBR (or any specific fragment) as one outcome. Then $P(\text{***Outcome}) = P(\text{Outcome})$, according to our early chapters. If $P(\text{***R}) = P(R)$, then $P(\text{***RBR})$ must be $= P(RBR)$ as well because R and RBR are both outcomes. An outcome can be a specific path of any length.

6.2 Any partially blind, partially specific paths

Let us make a list of steps, some sort of an algorithm, for solving such problems. (We can use **AB**C**CBA** as an example.)

1. Once we cross the blind field, we know the probability of the appearance of the first known element by the Blind Fair approach.
2. This first known outcome is removed from the path. The system is renewed and obtains new characteristics according to the action in the system. This is equivalent to "Given that this element was drawn and the impact of the associated action was applied to the system at that step".
3. If the further path is blind, then we use the Blind Fair approach and return to the initial point 1. The removal of the blind zone does not affect the following path because the blind cases do not change the proportions of the system.
4. If the further path is specific, then we know the probability of the appearance of the first known element and return to point 2.
5. When we reach the end of the path, we use the "easy formula" for finding the probability of one shrunk specific path (all the specific fragments stitched together) that we get at the end.

The conclusion here is this: when finding probabilities, all blind zones can be merely dropped from the original path.

Here is the second approach where, while moving forward, we consider all specific fragments as single events, fragment by fragment, to find the probability we are looking for.

Let us consider finding the probability of **ABA**BAA** in a system with A and B objects.

We can already simplify it because $P(\text{***ABA**BAA}) = P(\text{ABA**BAA})$. Let us represent the remaining path as **Outcome1**Outcome2** where **Outcome1** = **ABA**, **Outcome2** = **BAA**.

$P(\text{Outcome1**Outcome2}) = P(\text{Outcome1}) \times P(\text{***Outcome2, given that Outcome1 has taken place})$. According to the Blind Fair approach, $P(\text{***Outcome2, given that Outcome1 has taken place}) = P(\text{Outcome2, given that Outcome1 has taken place}) = P(\text{Outcome2} | \text{Outcome1})$.

Then $P(\text{***ABA**BAA}) = P(\text{Outcome1**Outcome2}) = P(\text{Outcome1}) \times P(\text{Outcome2} | \text{Outcome1}) = P(\text{Outcome1_Outcome2}) = P(\text{ABABAA})$.

Now we can generalize this approach. Let us agree that in a general path ****F₁**F₂** .. **F_{last}**** **F_i** stands for a specific fragment of sequentially drawn objects, and ****** stands for any number of joined blind objects (elsewhere in this paper, outside these proofs, ****** stands for two blind objects). Then $P(\text{**F}_1\text{**F}_2\text{** .. **F}_{\text{last}}\text{**}) = P(\text{**F}_1) \times P(\text{**F}_2\text{** .. **F}_{\text{last}}\text{**}, \text{ given that } \text{**F}_1 \text{ happened}) = |\text{the blind zone } \text{**} \text{ before } \text{F}_1 \text{ does not affect the following selections}| = P(\text{F}_1) \times P(\text{**F}_2\text{** .. **F}_{\text{last}}\text{**}, \text{ given that } \text{F}_1 \text{ happened}) = P(\text{F}_1) \times P(\text{**F}_2, \text{ given that } \text{F}_1 \text{ happened}) \times P(\text{**F}_3\text{** .. **F}_{\text{last}}\text{**}, \text{ given that } \text{**F}_2 \text{ happened, given that } \text{F}_1 \text{ happened}) = |\text{the blind zone } \text{**} \text{ before } \text{F}_2 \text{ does not affect the following selections}| = P$

$(F_1) \times P(F_2, \text{ given that } F_1 \text{ happened}) \times P(**F_3** \dots **F_{last}**, \text{ given that } F_2 \text{ happened, given that } F_1 \text{ happened}) = \dots$ |moving with the same procedure step by step| $= P(F_1) \times P(F_2, \text{ given that } F_1 \text{ happened}) \times \dots \times P(F_{last}**, \text{ given that } F_{second-last} \text{ happened, } \dots, \text{ given that } F_2 \text{ happened, given that } F_1 \text{ happened}) =$ |the blind zone ** at the very end of the path can be ignored as any remaining objects can fill those gaps and the probability of it equals 1| $= P(F_1) \times P(F_2, \text{ given that } F_1 \text{ happened}) \times P(F_3, \text{ given that } F_2 \text{ happened, given that } F_1 \text{ happened}) \times \dots \times P(F_{last}, \text{ given that } F_{second-last} \text{ happened, } \dots, \text{ given that } F_2 \text{ happened, given that } F_1 \text{ happened}) = P(F_1 F_2) \times P(F_3, \text{ given that } F_1 F_2 \text{ happened}) \times \dots \times P(F_{last}, \text{ given that } F_1 F_2 F_3 \dots F_{second-last} \text{ happened}) = P(F_1 F_2 F_3) \times P(F_4, \text{ given that } F_1 F_2 F_3 \text{ happened}) \times \dots \times P(F_{last}, \text{ given that } F_1 F_2 F_3 \dots F_{second-last} \text{ happened}) = \dots = P(F_1 F_2 \dots F_{last}).$
 Therefore, $P(**F_1**F_2** \dots **F_{last}**) = P(F_1 F_2 \dots F_{last}).$

We need to clarify that “given that F_2 happened, given that F_1 happened” means “given that F_1 happened first, then F_2 happened afterwards”. In terms of notation, this is reflected in $P(F_1 F_2 F_3) = P(F_3 | F_2 | F_1)$. Similarly, this applies to all longer constructions where the last mentioned outcome (in a long description or in a notation $F_3 | F_2 | F_1$) happens first, and everything moves sequentially backwards.

An approach with moving backwards in terms of split probabilities gives a shorter and somewhat more elegant proof. (“Event” in the proof below has the ordinary meaning and is not the probabilistic term.)

$P(**F_1**F_2** \dots **F_{last}**) = P(**F_1**F_2** \dots **F_{last}**) = P(**F_1**F_2** \dots **F_{second-last}**) \times P(**F_{last}$, given that the previous events happened)) $= P(**F_1**F_2** \dots **F_{third-last}**) \times P(**F_{second-last}$, given that the previous events happened) $\times P(**F_{last}$, given that the previous events happened) $= \dots = P(**F_1**) \times P(**F_2$, given that $**F_1$ event happened) $\times \dots \times P(**F_{second-last}$, given that the previous events happened) $\times P(**F_{last}$, given that the previous events happened) = |the blind zone ** in front of specific fragments do not affect the following events according to the similar shapes principle and therefore can be dropped within each factor| $= P(F_1) \times P(F_2, \text{ given that } F_1 \text{ event happened}) \times \dots \times P(F_{last}, \text{ given that the previous events happened}) = P(F_1 F_2) \times P(F_3, \text{ given that } F_1 F_2 \text{ event happened}) \times \dots \times P(F_{last}, \text{ given that the previous events happened}) = \dots = P(F_1 F_2 \dots F_{last}).$
 Thus, $P(**F_1**F_2** \dots **F_{last}**) = P(F_1 F_2 \dots F_{last}).$

There is one more proof approach where the whole remaining path at each step becomes one outcome. In order to avoid the excess of similar proofs this one is placed in [Appendix 2](#).

Yet, after many proofs, probably the best and simplest one is this. Let us agree that in a general path $**F_1**F_2** \dots **F_{last}**$ F_i stands for a specific fragment of sequentially drawn objects, and ** stands for any number of joined blind objects. Blind outcomes **, according to the similar shapes principle, fairly affect all groups and, while taking place, do not change the proportions of the updated at each step system. Therefore, they do not affect the probability of upcoming selections. For this reason, all blind zones can be dropped from the partially blind, partially specific path. The remaining specific fragments combine into a joint specific path, the probability of which is easy to find.

6.3 Blind Fair Impact Theorem for Specific Paths

All the above allows us to generate, and serves as a proof for, the following theorem.

Blind Fair Impact Theorem for Specific Paths

In probability systems with objects drawn where impacts are fair (same for any type of objects), and where some intermediate outcomes are unknown (an observer is blind towards them), the blind zones in such partially blind, partially specific paths can be dropped (ignored). The remaining specific fragments join, and create one united specific path of objects, the probability of which is easy to find.

The theorem holds even in a case when a fair impact modifies at new instances of drawing an object.

We have two key points here:

1. All blind gaps in the path can be ignored (dropped).
2. All remaining specific fragments create one joint specific path, the probability of which is easy to find.

The theorem provides interesting implications.

Consider, for example, a system with 8 red and 5 blue marbles. In this system

1. $P(\text{*****RB}) = P(\text{RB})$ for any possible length of the blind field.
2. $P(*\text{RB}) = P(\text{*****RB}) = \frac{8}{13} \times \frac{5}{12}$.
3. $P(*\text{R*****B}) = P(\text{*****RB})$.
4. The probability of getting a blue marble, given that one red was randomly chosen somewhere earlier, is $P(*[\text{R}]*****\text{B}) = P(\text{*****[R]B}) = P([\text{R]B}) = P(\text{B} | \text{R}) = \frac{5}{12}$.
5. $P(*\text{R**RB***R}) = P(\text{RRBR})$.

In all examples the blind fields can be of any possible length.

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Chapter 7. Blind Fair Impact and Combos - Blind Fair Impact Theorem for Combos

The Blind Fair Impact Phenomenon affects combos in the same way.

Blind Fair Impact Theorem for Combos

In probability systems with objects drawn where impacts are fair (same for any type of objects), the probability of a combo (a combination of types of objects) in a fragment of a path of drawn objects is not dependent on unknown preceding outcomes. It depends directly on the initial characteristics of the system, namely, proportions of the system that are given by the size of groups (types of objects) when all preceding selections of objects are unknown, or on the renewed characteristics of the system when some preceding selections in the path become known.

The theorem holds even in the cases when a fair impact modifies at new instances of drawing an object.

Terms “outcomes” and “selections of objects” (features of selected objects) in the theorem are interchangeable.

Proof: Let us prove the theorem for environments with sampling without replacement first. We will use an example first and then generalize it.

There is a system of 10 aquamarine, 10 blue, and 10 crimson coloured marbles. They all have the same shape and texture. One marble is drawn at a time without looking, it is not returned to the system. The first five results have gone unrecorded. Find the probability that among the 6th to 10th randomly selected marbles there will be 3 aquamarine, 1 blue, and 1 crimson ones. (The spots of interest can also be made non-sequential. It could be, for example, the 3rd and 4th, the 6th, the 9th and 10th marbles.)

We need to show that the first five picks with unknown results do not alter the probability of the following combo, and that this problem is equivalent to finding the probability of the required combo in just five picks.

Let us randomly distribute all 30 marbles into 30 sequential spots, one by one, not simultaneously. (Simultaneous scattering makes this proof even easier and stronger, but such systems are not considered in this paper.) Since their distribution is random, the 10 aquamarine marbles (type A) can take any 10 spots in 30 available; the same applies to 10 blue and 10 crimson ones. Therefore, every possible path (sequence) of marble **types** has the same probability of appearing. Since the five spots from #6 to #10 receive random marbles, they are equivalent to the first five spots because the first five spots receive equally random marble types.

The probability of getting the required types of marbles in the first five spots is the same as the probability of this desired combo in just five drawings. Thus, the probability of getting a combo in the middle of a path is not dependent on the preceding blind outcomes.

There is a “more formal” proof for this example in [Appendix 3](#).

This approach works for any number of types, any number of objects within types, and any combos. Therefore it generalizes.

It needs to be mentioned that the same proof approach can be used for specific paths. But whether this approach is used for combos or specific paths, it only works for cases of sampling without replacement. Later on we will give a proof for systems with actions that are different from sampling without replacement.

It is also clear that in the case of two fragments with two different combos, the probability of the first fragment needs to be found first because chronologically it takes place first. The blind zone in front of it can be dropped according to our above-mentioned reasoning. Then the second fragment finds itself in a modified environment (given that the first fragment has taken place). Now we can find its probability in this new environment. And again, the blind zone in front of it can be dropped since we now continue anew in a fresh environment. Overall, the probability of the second fragment becomes conditional because it is affected by the first fragment.

We will modify the previous problem here in order to illustrate the above. Find the probability that in random selections from # 5 to # 9 there will be a combo of 3 A, 1 B,

and 1 C marbles, and in selections from # 19 to # 24 there will be a different combo of 3 A, 1 B, and 2 C marbles, given that selections from # 1 to # 4, and from # 10 to # 18, have gone unrecorded and are therefore unknown.

All the blind zones can be excluded from the whole path of the selections. After the blind zones are dropped, we get two islands of combos for which we need to separately calculate their probabilities (the second probability becoming conditional) and multiply them.

$P(\text{Combo 1} \cap \text{Combo 2}) = P(\text{Combo 1}) \times P(\text{Combo 2} \mid \text{Combo 1}) = P(\text{Combo 1}) \times P(\text{Combo 2, given that Combo 1 has taken place}) = | \text{For Combo 1: } 10,10,10 \rightarrow 3,1,1. \text{ For Combo 2, given that Combo 1 has taken place: } 7,9,9 \rightarrow 3,1,2| = (C_3^{10} \times C_1^{10} \times C_1^{10} \div C_5^{30}) \times (C_3^7 \times C_1^9 \times C_2^9 \div C_6^{25}) = 0.0054 \text{ (4 dp)}.$

We already saw an example of using combinations in solving problems of this kind at the beginning of Chapter 3.

In Chapter 4 Section 4, we saw that the Blind Fair Impact phenomenon works for specific paths even when a fair action modifies at each step. This gives us a tool for proving the Blind Fair Impact phenomenon for combos in the case of all fair actions (not sampling without replacement only), whether they are invariant at each step or not.

Indeed, any combo consists of all specific paths that are possible within it. Its probability is the sum of probabilities of all such specific paths. For example, in a 2A,2B system, the combo 1A,1B in the 3rd and 4th instances of four selections consists of two possible specific paths: **AB and **BA. Each of these paths is not dependent on the preceding blind outcomes, whether a fair action varies at different instances of selections or not. Their probabilities can be found from the straight away occurrences of AB and BA. The probabilities of “straight away” specific paths add up, and make the probability of the “straight away” combo 1A,1B in the first two instances of four selections, which is simply the combo of 1A,1B objects drawn in two selection attempts out of 2A,2B.

As this approach can include any number of groups with any number of objects in them, and can be applied to any fragment in the path, this proof generalizes. The proof is now complete.

When fair impacts keep changing prior to the combo, but the combo itself undergoes a sampling without replacement, its probability is easy to find. But when changing fair actions, or invariant actions different from sampling without replacement, step into the combo as well, finding its probability becomes a challenge. As mentioned earlier, it is very likely possible to produce combinations formulae for both such cases. As a last resort, it is always possible to find the probability of any combo by adding the probabilities of all its constituents, specific paths, although such a task can be very time consuming.

Thus, in a system with Blind Fair Impact, the probability of a combo of objects is not affected by preceding selections with unknown results.

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Chapter 8. General Blind Fair Impact Theorem

The Blind Fair Impact Lemma and Theorems for Specific Paths and Combos can be brought together to give the general description of the Blind Fair Impact phenomenon.

General Blind Fair Impact Theorem

In finding probabilities in systems with objects drawn, where some intermediate outcomes are unknown, and the impact of an action after each instance of drawing is fair (same for any type of objects), the blind zones in the path can be dropped (ignored). The probability of an outcome, whether it is single or complex, in such systems is not affected by the unknown preceding outcomes but depends directly on the initial characteristics of a system, namely, proportions of the system that are given by the size of groups (types of objects) when all preceding selections of objects are unknown, or on the renewed characteristics of the system when some preceding selections in the path become known.

Terms “outcomes” and “selections of objects” (features of selected objects) in the theorem are interchangeable.

Since the content of the General Blind Fair Impact Theorem combines the contents of the Lemma for single outcomes and Theorems for specific paths and combos, the combination of proofs of the Lemma and the two Theorems become the proof of this general theorem.

For an application of this theorem, let us modify a problem we used in the previous chapter. This time we include a specific path and a combo.

There is a system of 10 aquamarine, 10 blue, and 10 crimson coloured marbles. They all have the same shape and texture. One marble is drawn at a time without looking, it is not returned to the system. Find the probability that the 5th marble drawn is aquamarine, the 6th is crimson, and in random selections from # 10 to # 15 there is a combo of 2 aquamarine, 1 blue, and 3 crimson marbles, given that selections from # 1 to # 4, and from # 7 to # 9, have gone unrecorded and are therefore unknown.

According to the Blind Fair Impact Theorems for Specific Paths and Combos $P(\text{****AC***}[2A,1B,3C]) = P(\text{AC}[2A,1B,3C]) = P(\text{AC}) \times P(2A,1B,3C, \text{ given that AC appeared earlier})$ | For the specific path: $P(\text{AC}) = \frac{10}{30} \times \frac{10}{29}$. For the combo in the new environment, after 1A and 1C have been removed from the system: $9,10,9 \rightarrow 2,1,3$ | $(\frac{10}{30} \times \frac{10}{29}) \times (C_2^9 \times C_1^{10} \times C_3^9 \div C_6^{28}) = 0.009$ (3 dp).

One of the implications and practical outcomes of this investigation is that we do not need probability trees for solving problems where objects are selected from a system (see Problem 3 in Chapter 9). When we work with a specific path along a probability tree, we can simply use an “easy formula” that covers the path. When we have blind zones, they all can get dropped, and we get a specific path again. When we find the probabilities of combos, we can use a combinations formula similarly to how we did it in this paper. It looks like the majority of problems in probability textbooks about selecting objects from a system can be solved without the use of probability trees.

Nonetheless, probability trees are still helpful in visualizing a problem and the probability system it belongs to, and in representing all the details of the system. They are useful when a system is being investigated and explored. On the other hand, if a

system has many rounds of selections, then drawing a big tree becomes [tedious and time consuming.

In conclusion, the major findings of this investigation can be stated as follows:

1. When applied actions are fair to all groups in a system with drawing objects, a blind zone at the beginning can be ignored in the process of finding the probability of the following outcome, whether the outcome is a single object or a group of objects (in some or without any order). Its probability can be found directly from the initial proportions of the groups in the system.
2. In complex paths of specific outcomes with unknown selections in between all blind zones can be ignored and dropped in the process of finding the probabilities of specific outcomes.
3. Probability trees for solving problems in systems with objects drawn are not needed anymore due to an “easy formula” that follows the path, a combinations formula that applies to a combo, or the straight away answer for a single outcome. All the obscurity zones in such systems get addressed, and a system converts into one with only specific outcomes.

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Chapter 9. Interesting applications of the phenomenon in probability problems

Problem 1. There is a set of letters comprising the alphabet, 26 plastic squares with a unique letter written on each one of them. For the convenience of making sentences, 5 more empty squares are added to the set. The squares have the same size and shape. All squares have been drawn one by one, without looking, from a container and placed one after another to make a “sentence”. Find the probability that the last four letters in the “sentence” read MATHS.

Solution: $P(\text{*****MATHS}) = P(\text{MATHS}) = \frac{1}{31} \times \frac{1}{30} \times \frac{1}{29} \times \frac{1}{28} \times \frac{1}{27} = \frac{1}{20,389,320}$.

Problem 2 ^[9]. 5 socks, 3 blue and 2 green, are in a drawer by themselves. Socks are taken out of the drawer one at a time, without looking, until either all the blue socks are out or both the green socks are out. What is the probability that the last sock drawn is green?

Before we proceed, try solving this problem on your own using classical solutions, and then we will try the Blind Fair approach as well.

Solution: Let us draw all five socks, one by one, in spite of the rules. If both green socks are taken out first, then there are still some blue socks, at least one, left in the drawer. This means that the fifth sock taken from the drawer is definitely blue. “At least one” indicates that we should consider only the fifth position taken by blue socks. And indeed, if the green socks “win the race”, then the fifth sock must be blue. The opposite is also true: if the last sock is blue, then all greens are taken out somewhere earlier; they are done **within the first four drawn socks**. So the probability that all green socks are taken out first is the probability that the fifth sock drawn is blue.

Thus, the probability that the last sock drawn is green, $P(\text{green socks are taken out first}) = P(\text{fifth sock drawn is blue}) = P(\text{****B}) = P(B) = P(\text{first sock drawn is blue}) = \frac{3}{5}$.

It can be understood that these probabilities equalize coincidentally; it happened that their values are the same. Yet, when we put the question of the problem and the answer together, it starts looking unreal: the probability that we get green socks first (before all blue socks are gone) equals the probability that the first sock drawn is blue!

We will cover in detail this interesting seeming controversy in one of the following papers.

This problem illustrates a clear difference between classical approaches and the Blind Fair approach in terms of solution. With the probability tree approach, there is a move that progresses from left to right. It deals with numerous uncertain paths from the outset and must encompass the entire “story”, all five steps. Similarly, the combinatorial approach (which, by the way, gives a beautiful answer: $\frac{C_1^1 + C_1^2 + C_1^3}{C_2^5}$) also addresses

numerous combinations from the outset and must cover the entire “story”, all five positions. On the contrary, the Blind Fair approach moves from right to left. It starts from the end and stops there because the answer is already found. It uses the single certain event at the very end, which is already the final step in the whole “story”.

Problem 3. Let us see one more time a comparison between a conventional way of solving a probability problem and the Blind Fair approach. Once again, we will use the problem that triggered the whole investigation, this time slightly modified.

A hat holds 7 blue and 4 yellow marbles. A marble is picked without looking, and then returned into the hat with two more marbles of the same colour. Then 3 more marbles are picked one by one with the same action of returning each with two extra marbles. Work out the probability that the third marble picked is blue, and the fourth one is yellow.

Figure 9-1. Probability tree for Problem 3

From the probability tree

getting “prize A and prize C” combo is higher when they draw tickets at the beginning, or at the very end?

According to the findings in this paper, there is no need to even calculate the probabilities. They are the same for both options, and whether the couple decides to draw tickets at the beginning, in the middle, or at the very end, the chances of getting the “prize A and prize C” combo stay exactly the same.

This solution is a bit counterintuitive as one may argue: “There are only 4 prizes A. There are more chances to get a prize A at the beginning than at the very end, when 16 prizes out of 18 have been already taken”. This is logical, on one hand. On the other hand, there are a lot of prizes B and C at the very beginning, and it is mainly them that will be picked within the first drawings.

Even if there were only one prize A in the whole set, the chance of obtaining it at the very beginning is exactly the same as getting this prize at the very last pick. Again, this is counterintuitive, because naturally it looks like the chances of getting the unique A at the very last pick become smaller and smaller, while more and more guests draw their tickets.

$$P(\text{prize A at the first pick}) = \frac{1}{17}$$

$$P(\text{prize A at the last pick}) = \frac{16}{17} (\text{any prize but A at the first pick}) \times \frac{15}{16} (\text{any prize but A at the second pick}) \times \frac{14}{15} \times \dots \times \frac{2}{3} \times \frac{1}{2} (\text{any prize but A at the second last pick}) \times \frac{1}{1} (\text{prize A at the last pick}) = \frac{1}{17}$$

Their probabilities are the same.

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Naming the phenomenon

I could not find the awareness of this phenomenon in sources online. The very fact that competition problems, mentioned in this paper, can be solved so trivially with the help of this phenomenon may indicate that mathematicians nowadays are not familiar with it. Even in the case that it was observed and described in the past, this research may still reveal more features of the phenomenon, and provide some further insight into it. Ways of applying the phenomenon to probability problems could be found interesting as well.

If this phenomenon is something new, then I propose to name it *Haonanz*. The student who stumbled upon it is talented in mathematics; his full name is Haonan Zhu. At the time of this accidental discovery he was only 13 years old. It looks like he intuitively sensed the equality of different action problems in their probability trees. Later, this brought in a further discovery: the blind zones in such environments can be completely ignored, and, therefore, the final probabilities can be found straight away. Besides, this happened in New Zealand, so NZ (at the end of *Haonanz*) is a very organic part of this proposed phenomenon’s name.

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Appendices

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Appendix 2

A proof for Section 6.2 *Any partially blind, partially specific paths* with an approach where the whole remaining path at each step becomes one outcome.

Consider a path ABAB**BAA****B***AA*AAA. In this path the probability $P(\text{ABAB**BAA****B***AA*AAA}) = P(\text{ABAB}) \times P(\text{**BAA****B***AA*AAA, given that ABAB has taken place})$.

BAA**B***AA*AAA is a shortened original path. Let us consider BAA****B***AA*AAA as Subpath1. $P(\text{**Subpath1}) = P(\text{Subpath1})$; the blind zone ** at the beginning does not affect the following selections. Then the process of finding the probability of BAA****B***AA*AAA under a certain condition (the condition being ABAB) becomes exactly the same as finding the probability of the whole path. It generates $P = P(\text{BAA}) \times P(\text{****Subpath2, given that BAA has taken place, where Subpath2} = \text{B***AA*AAA})$, the certain condition being that ABAB has taken place. The process will repeat until there are no fragments (ABAB, BAA, B, AA, AAA) left. The probability of each specific fragment contributes as a factor to the probability of the whole path. In our case we get:

$P(\text{ABAB**BAA****B***AA*AAA}) = P(\text{ABAB}) \times P(\text{BAA, given that ABAB has taken place})$ [this equals to $P(\text{ABABBAA})$] $\times P(\text{B, given that ABABBAA has taken place}) \times P(\text{AA, given that ABABBAAAB has taken place}) \times P(\text{AAA, given that ABABBAAABAA has taken place}) = P(\text{ABABAABABAABAAA})$.

We can extend this approach to any number of specific fragments in the path, therefore obtaining a proof for the general case of partially blind, partially specific paths.

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Appendix 3

Supplementary proof for Chapter 7.

There is a system of 10 aquamarine, 10 blue, and 10 crimson coloured marbles. They all have the same shape and texture. One marble is drawn at a time without looking, it is not returned to the system. The first five results have gone unrecorded and are therefore unknown. Find the probability that among the 6th to 10th randomly selected marbles there will be 3 aquamarine, 1 blue, and 1 crimson ones.

We need to show that the first five picks with unknown results do not alter the probability of the following combo, and that this problem is equivalent to finding the probability of the required combo in just five picks.

Let us randomly distribute all 30 marbles into 30 sequential spots, one by one, not simultaneously. A marble of an arbitrary type can appear in any of the 30 spots. This means that in five selected spots there can be marbles of any type. Now, there is a certain number of all possible combinations of specific objects within a desired combo of types. In our case $(10,10,10 \rightarrow 3,1,1)$ this number is $C_3^{10} \times C_1^{10} \times C_1^{10} = 12000$. The number of such combinations in spots #6 to #10 is exactly the same with spots #1 to #5. Then the probability of our combo appearing in spots #6 to #10 is exactly the same with spots #1 to #5. Both probabilities equal the same fraction of the number of combinations of objects within a desired combo **in** the number of combinations of n

objects (size of the combo) within all objects in the system. In our case this probability

$$\text{is } \frac{C_3^{10} \times C_1^{10} \times C_1^{10}}{C_5^{30}} .$$

The probability of getting a combo in the middle of a path is the same as getting this combo in the first five spots, which, in turn, is the probability of this desired combo in just five picks. Therefore, the first selections with unknown results do not alter the probability of the following combo. Thus, the probability of getting a combo in the middle of a path is not dependent on the preceding blind outcomes.

Since this proof applies to any number of types, any number of objects within types, and any combos, it generalizes. The proof is now complete.

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Further investigations

In this paper we have covered cases when an action after drawing an object applies to the group of the same type. It would be interesting to see whether the phenomenon still works under different arrangements. For example, when types of objects are numbered, and drawing an object of one type sets off an action for the next type (in the numbered list of types). Or, drawing an object of one type sets off the action to all other types but leaves the selected type itself without change.

Also, in this research we drew only one object from a system at a time. Drawing two or more objects simultaneously with applying an action to all selected types would be another interesting line of further investigation.

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